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Homoeopathy and non-communicable diseases: An integrated approach

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Abstract

An epidemiological transition is evident in low- and middle-income nations, such as India, where non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and accidents are displacing communicable diseases as the leading causes of disability, morbidity, and premature mortality. Nowadays, globally, non-communicable illnesses are a significant problem. Non-communicable diseases (NCDs), sometimes referred to as chronic diseases, are often long-lasting and caused by a confluence of behavioral, physiological, environmental, and genetic variables. More than 75% of NCD deaths worldwide occur in low- and middle-income nations, where individuals are disproportionately affected by these diseases.

Keywords: Non-communicable diseases; Homoeopathy; Lifestyle disorders; Chronic diseases

1. Introduction

Chronic illnesses that cannot be spread from one person to another are known as non-communicable diseases (NCDs). An extensive spectrum of acute and chronic medical conditions, such as cancer, diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases and stroke, chronic kidney diseases (CKDs), chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (COPDs) and asthma, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), and several kinds of other illnesses, may be considered NCDs if this definition is taken into consideration.⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾

Cancer, diabetes, high blood pressure, heart disease, stroke, chronic renal disease, chronic obstructive lung disease, psychological disorders, and trauma are the main causes. In addition to being a major public health concern, NCDs impede the nation's socioeconomic advancement.⁽³⁾

1.1. Epidemiology

In both industrialised and developing nations, the prevalence of chronic non-communicable diseases among adults is rising. At present, the two main causes of death in affluent nations are cancer and cardiovascular disorders.⁽¹⁾ About 8.8 million people die from cancer each year, followed by respiratory illnesses (about 3.9 million deaths) and diabetes (1.6 million morbidities yearly). Among all NCDs, these four disease categories are the leading causes of mortality.⁽⁴⁾

Numerous factors, such as urbanisation, changes in lifestyle, and an ageing population, are responsible for the growth in NCDs. For example, sedentary lifestyles, elevated anxiety levels, and dietary patterns heavy in sugar and saturated fats are associated with cardiovascular illnesses. Because of an increase in obesity and a decline in physical activity, the prevalence of diabetes has increased.⁽¹⁾

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Since 2000, when there were 31 million fatalities from NCDs, the number of deaths from NCDs has increased globally and in every region. The WHO South-East Asia Region saw the largest increase in NCD mortality, rising from 6.7 million in 2000 to 8.5 million in 2012, while the Western Pacific Region saw the largest increase, rising from 8.6 million to 10.9 million. The total number of NCD fatalities is expected to rise to 52 million by 2030, even while the number of deaths from infectious diseases is predicted to reduce.⁽⁵⁾

1.2. Risk Factors

Risk factors can be classified in one approach as either modifiable or non-modifiable, depending on whether their circumstances are changeable or not. The following are the risk factors: Obesity, physical inactivity, diabetes mellitus, high blood pressure, smoking, and high blood cholesterol; the non-modifiable risk factors include age, gender, genetics, race, and ethnicity⁽⁶⁾

Youngsters, adults, and the elderly are all susceptible to lifestyle-related risk factors that increase the burden of noncommunicable diseases, which affect the quality of life index and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). Due to the population's poor lifestyle, unplanned urbanization, and globalization, the incidence of these diseases is rising quickly⁽⁷⁾

2. Lifestyle Diseases

- Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs)
- Stroke
- Respiratory diseases
- Diabetes

2.1. Cardiovascular Diseases (CVDs)⁽¹⁾

Heart and vascular system disorders are collectively referred to as cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Congenital heart disease, cerebrovascular disease (stroke), hypertension, and ischaemic heart disease (IHD) are the main ailments. In many underdeveloped nations, rheumatic heart disease (RHD) remains a significant health issue.

2.2. Stroke⁽³⁾

Acute severe symptoms of cerebro-vascular disease are referred to as "stroke" or "apoplexy." It disables people mentally and physically. The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines stroke as "Clinical symptoms of impairment of cerebral function; lasting more than one day or leading to death, with no obvious cause other than vascular origin."

2.3. Respiratory Diseases

A wide range of disorders affecting the airways and other parts of the lungs are referred to as chronic respiratory diseases. As people age, the majority of CRD morbidity and death increases. Asthma, COPD, respiratory allergies, pulmonary hypertension, and occupational lung diseases are examples of CRDs⁽⁶⁾

2.4. Diabetes⁽¹⁾⁽³⁾

Diabetes, one of which was once thought to be a single disease entity, is today recognised as a diverse set of diseases that are characterized by a persistently high blood sugar level. These diseases are caused by a variety of environmental and genetic factors that work together. Defective insulin production or activity, a hormone that regulates the metabolism of glucose, fat, and amino acids, is the root cause of diabetes. Diabetes is typically a chronic condition with a range of clinical signs and symptoms. Regardless of the reason, persistent hyperglycemia causes a variety of problems, including neurological, ophthalmic, renal, cardiovascular, and other issues such as concurrent infections.

2.5. Homoeopathic view

Instead of treating the illness, homoeopathy treats the patient. We treat every patient in a holistic approach according to their physical as well as their mental symptoms. To find out the perfect simillimum medicine which one is the most similar to the 'the totality of the symptoms' of the patient by using 'law of similia' after considering the patient as a whole from our large number of homoeopathic medicines⁽⁸⁾

It can be carried out using the principles of Homoeopathy as instructed by our master in the Organon of Medicine, in § 4 Hahnemann says that "If a person is aware of the things that disrupt health and cause sickness and knows how to remove them from healthy people, he is also a health preserver".

In § 5 he says, "The information regarding the most likely exciting cause of the acute disease, as well as the most important points in the entire history of the chronic disease, can be helpful to the physician in helping him to cure, as they enable him to discover its fundamental cause, which is generally due to a chronic miasm.". The concept of 'specific remedy' is given by Hahnemann in **§ 102 (footnote)**, "Homeopathic medicines are highly effective when it comes to prevention of diseases/ disorders." ⁽⁸⁾⁽⁹⁾

3. Rubrics from Boericke's Repertory Related to Ncds ^[10]

- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM: ARTERIES- Atheroma of arteries (arteriosclerosis):
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, ARTERIES- Degeneration, fatty:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, ARTERIES- Dilatation: Aneurism:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, ARTERIES- Dilatation: Aneurism, capillary:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, RUPTURE of artery (apoplexy):
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, HEART-Action tumultuous, violent, labored:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, HEART- AFFECTIONS in general:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, HEART- affections, rheumatic:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, DEGENERATION- fatty:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, HYPERTROPHY:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, HYPERTROPHY-Hypertrophy uncomplicated, of athletes:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, INFLAMMATION (ENDOCARDITIS)- Acute:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, INFLAMMATION- malignant:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, MYOCARDITIS: CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, PERICARDITIS:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, PAIN, Neuralgic, ANGINA PECTORIS:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, VALVULAR DISEASE:
- CIRCULATORY SYSTEM, PALPITATION, CAUSE, Tobacco

3.1. In Kent Repertory ⁽¹¹⁾

- CHEST- AFFECTIONS OF THE- Heart
- CHEST- AFFECTIONS OF THE- Heart Over lifting
- CHEST- FATTY degeneration of heart
- GENERALITIES- TUMORS- atheroma

3.2. In A Concise Repertory of Homoeopathic Medicines by Dr S. R. Pathak ⁽¹²⁾

- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS
- BLOOD PRESSURE- High BLOOD PRESSURE-
- Sudden rise of BLOOD PRESSURE-
- Low BLOOD PRESSURE-
- Low- Diastolic
- BLOOD VESSELS- Affections of in general
- FATTY- Degeneration
- HEART- Endocarditis
- HEART- Fatty degeneration
- HEART- Palpitation
- HEART- Palpitation- Head, beating in, with

3.3. In Synthesis Repertory ⁽¹³⁾

- CHEST- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS of coronaries
- CHEST- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS of coronaries- old people; in men; old
- CHEST- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS of coronariestobacco; from
- CHEST- WEAKNESS-Heart- arteriosclerosis,in
- GENERALS- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS

- GENERALS- ARTERIOSCLEROSIS- old people; in
- GENERAL- FATTY DEGENERATION- blood vessels; of
- GENERALS- HYPERLIPIDEMIA
- GENERALS- HYPERLIPIDEMIA; dialysis; from

4. Homoeopathic Medicines for Non Communicable Diseases ⁽¹⁰⁾

4.1. Vanadium Metallicum

Raises haemoglobin levels and mixes oxygen with toxins to eliminate their virulence. boosts and activates phagocytes as well. A treatment for liver and artery degenerative diseases.

4.2. Gymnema Sylvestre

Reduces sugar in the urine, the patient gains weight and muscle, and their hunger increases. Prolongs a diabetic patient's life. All signs and symptoms are accompanied by a burning feeling.

4.3. Ignatia Amara

Apprehension brought on by shock, grief, or psychological discomfort.

4.4. Bothrops Lanceolatus

Inability to speak without using their tongue affectionately. hemorrhages, with fluid, black blood. Breathing was suppressed, and there was more or less bloody expectoration, this is one of the indications of pulmonary congestion. paralysis of only one arm or leg.⁽¹⁴⁾

5. Conclusion

In addition to other necessary medications, homoeopathy can be used safely and has plenty of potential for curing non-communicable diseases. The man is affected inside by homoeopathic treatment, which is tailored to each individual based on their constitution. Also, it is essential to make a concerted effort to decrease sedentary lifestyles and break negative habits like inactivity and eating disorders, which have been ingrained in contemporary lifestyles and have been found to be the main contributors to the development of NCDs.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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